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Trade-Offs in Public Support for Climate Action? The Role of Environmental and Economic Shocks

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Abstract

Public support for climate policies depends on how people prioritize environmental concerns over other issues. While experiencing climate change and related extreme events can raise environmental concerns, economic disruptions can shift attention away from environmental issues. Using 36 waves of Eurobarometer surveys (2003-2023) merged with regional economic and climate data, we examine how external economic and environmental shocks shape public concerns across 339 European subnational regions in 35 countries. Fixed effects panel regressions reveal evidence for the existence of trade-offs: Environmental shocks increase environmental concerns while reducing economic concerns, consistent with the finite pool of worry hypothesis. Economic shocks, on the other hand, increase economic concerns and decrease environmental concerns, although to a lesser extent. If both shocks co-occur, respondents typically prioritize economic over environmental issues. These trade-off patterns vary across demographic groups and regional contexts. The findings demonstrate that public attention to environmental issues is responsive to external shocks and highlights the need to design environmental policies and communication strategies that remain politically viable also under adverse economic conditions.

1. Introduction

Public support for climate action is widely recognized as essential for advancing effective climate change and adaptation strategies (Drews & van den Bergh, 2016). Over the past years, levels of support and concern about climate change have generally increased, reflecting heightened awareness of its risks and consequences (Hoffmann et al., 2022; Peisker, 2023). At the same time, fluctuations in environmental concern remain evident, particularly in periods marked by other pressing challenges.

In particular, economic shocks can divert attention and create priorities that run counter to sustainability goals. A trade-off between economic and environmental concern has been documented (Inglehart, 1981, 1995), especially during periods of economic downturns or uncertainty (Kahn & Kotchen, 2011; Scruggs & Benegal, 2012; Shum, 2012). During such times, individuals tend to prioritize immediate economic needs and financial security over longer-term environmental commitments.

This trade-off is captured most prominently by the 'finite pool of worry' hypotheses, which suggests that individuals have limited cognitive and emotional resources and therefore prioritize their concerns in times of crisis. When economic anxiety rises, driven, for instance, by unemployment or inflation, attention to other issues such as climate change tends to diminish (Marx et al., 2007; Sisco et al., 2023; Weber, 2006). Empirical evidence lends support to this view: major economic shocks, including the 2008 financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic, have been shown to temporarily suppress both environmental concern and support for climate policies (M. Bergquist et al., 2023; Ecker et al., 2020).

However, to date, there is limited comparative evidence on how different types of external shocks can either amplify concerns or divert them. Moreover, little is known about how contextual factors shape the extent of this trade-off. Existing studies often rely on cross-sectional or national-level data, which restricts insights into regional variation and the longer-term dynamics of concern. Understanding these dynamics and the underlying drivers of public concerns is crucial for designing climate policies that are not only effective, but also resilient in maintaining public support in times of multiple, overlapping crises.

To this end, this study investigates how both economic and environmental shocks shape public prioritization of economic or climate and environmental issues across European regions. To do so, we construct a novel panel dataset harmonizing 36 waves of the Standard Eurobarometer survey conducted between 2003 and 2023. In the survey, respondents are asked to name the two main issues faced by the country at the moment, which we categorized into seven broad concern categories. These include concerns for the economy, the climate and environment, immigration, security issues, education, health, and pensions.

The survey data, aggregated at the NUTS-2 regional level, are merged with regional economic indicators from the Annual Regional Database of the European Commission's Directorate General for Regional and Urban Policy (ARDECO) and ERA5 reanalysis climate data from the Copernicus Climate Data Store. These are used to construct measures for external economic and environmental shocks, operationalized in form of changes in unemployment and temperature anomalies in the respondents' NUTS-2 regions.

The resulting dataset covers 35 countries and 339 subnational regions, providing unique opportunities to capture both spatial and temporal variation in public concerns. This design enables a comparative assessment of how different shocks interact with contextual conditions to influence concern, thereby extending existing evidence beyond single-country or cross-sectional analyses. Our

main outcome variables are the proportion of respondents in each region who identify the economy or the climate and environment among their top two policy concerns.

Using fixed effects panel regression models, we examine changes in concerns over time and in response to external economic and environmental shocks. The data allow us to investigate whether and under what conditions the economy and environment are perceived as competing or complementary priorities. We find that both types of shocks exert significant effects on the distribution of concerns, with economic shocks exerting a positive effect on economic concerns, and environmental shocks on environmental concerns. We furthermore find evidence that economic concerns decrease in response to environmental stress and environmental concerns in response to economic difficulties, in line with the notion of a trade-off between both aspects. If both shocks co-occur, respondents typically prioritize economic over environmental issues. The patterns differ across demographic groups and regional contexts, suggesting that both play important roles in moderating the shock-concern relationship.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature and introduces our theoretical framework. Section 3 describes the datasets and key measures and outlines our analytical approach. Section 4 presents the results. Section 5 discusses our main findings and their implications, and Section 6 concludes.

2. Theoretical framework and previous literature

Concerns are important drivers of behavioural change, shaping individuals' intentions and decisions to act (Leiserowitz, 2006; van der Linden, 2015). This is particularly true in the domains of environmental protection and climate change action, where broad public engagement and support are essential to achieve a more sustainable future (Clayton et al., 2015). In this study, we define concern as the conscious recognition of the significance of an issue, such as climate change, coupled with the perceived need to respond to it (Franzen & Bahr, 2024).

Research has shown that experiencing disruptive events, such as disasters or extreme climatic events, can significantly alter people's awareness and concerns (P. Bergquist & Warshaw, 2019; Brooks et al., 2014; Broomell et al., 2015; Dai et al., 2015; Hamilton & Stampone, 2013; Hoffmann et al., 2022). First-hand experience of such events reduces the psychological distance between individuals and the potential consequences of climate change, thereby increasing salience of the issue (Jones et al., 2017; Spence et al., 2012b, 2012a). In contrast, when individuals are not directly affected, the impact on perceptions and concerns tends to be weaker (Hoffmann et al., 2024).

While affect and emotion can act as powerful drivers of behavioural change (Brosch, 2021; Stollberg & Jonas, 2021), researchers have warned that negative emotions, such as fear, anxiety, or a sense of helplessness can sometimes have counterproductive effects. By undermining perceived efficacy, disruptive events could therefore reduce rather than foster environmental concerns and sustainable behaviours (Mathers-Jones & Todd, 2023; Peisker & Schinko, 2023). Moreover, individuals are not affected uniformly by such shocks: personal characteristics and personality traits all play important roles in shaping how environmental shocks influence concerns and willingness to act (Markowitz et al., 2012).

Beyond the experience of environmental shocks, other contextual influences can play a critical role (Franzen & Vogl, 2013; Marquart-Pyatt, 2012; Mildenerger & Leiserowitz, 2017; Peisker, 2023). Other disruptive events and crises can divert attention away from environmental issues, making them appear less urgent in the broader societal context (Birkland, 1998). In particular, economic shocks have been suggested in being influential in shifting individuals' and societies' priorities toward short-term material and financial concerns (Aklin & Urpelainen, 2013; Finseraas et al., 2021; Shum, 2012). Economic insecurity can foster a focus on immediate economic and income stability, which may crowd out willingness to invest in or support longer-term sustainability goals.

Studies suggest that during times of recession or financial crisis (Inglehart, 1981), public concern for the environment often declines as other issues, such as employment, wages, and inflation, become more pressing (Kahn & Kotchen, 2011; Maslow, 1943; Scruggs & Benegal, 2012; Shum, 2012). At the individual level, financial stress can limit people's perceived ability to engage in sustainable behaviours, while at the societal level, it can reduce political momentum for ambitious climate policies (Dienes, 2015; Duijndam & van Beukering, 2021). Disruptive events can therefore have a dual effect: while some crises heighten environmental awareness, others may suppress it by redirecting attention and resources toward competing priorities.

The Finite Pool of Worry (FPW) hypothesis provides a theoretical basis for understanding the trade-off between environmental and economic concerns. It suggests that humans possess limited emotional resources for worry, such that heightened concern about one threat diminishes concern about others (Simon, 1957; Weber, 2006). More recently, scholars have emphasized the related notion of a Finite Pool of Attention (FPA), which constrains people's awareness to a restricted set of issues, with attention preceding the formation of concern. According to this perspective, when individuals devote greater attention to one threat, their attention to other threats necessarily declines (Sisco et al., 2023).

In contrast, the affect generalization hypothesis (Johnson & Tversky, 1983) suggests that concerns about one issue, such as environmental change, can also spill over to related domains and generate additional worries. This effect occurs when an initial emotional response shapes perceptions of other issues considered similar or connected to the original event. For instance, extreme environmental events may not only heighten concern about the environment itself but also be perceived as threats to the economy, thereby amplifying both environmental and economic concerns.

In our theoretical framework (Figure 1), economic and environmental shocks are assumed to shape perceptions and beliefs, which in turn influence individuals' attention to and concern for specific issues. The strength of this relationship is moderated by both contextual factors, such as the general economic condition, political dynamics, and demographic characteristics, and individual characteristics, including age, sex, education, and the personal economic situation. These moderating factors determine a person's susceptibility to external threats and thus condition how shocks translate into concerns.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the role of shocks for public concerns. *The figure shows the potential effects of economic and environmental shocks on concerns via changes in perceptions and beliefs. Contextual and individual factors play a key role in shaping the vulnerability of affected individuals to the shocks and may hence moderate the relationships between shocks on one side and concerns on the other.*

Based on our theoretical framework and the existing literature, we hypothesize (Box 1) that each type of shock, when experienced in isolation, increases the corresponding concern (H1 & H2). When shocks of different types occur simultaneously, however, we expect a crowding out effect, whereby heightened concern for one issue diminishes concern for the other (H3). In contrast, if worries generalize across domains, we expect both types of shocks to amplify both environmental and economic concerns (H4). Moreover, both contextual and individual factors are expected to moderate these relationships (H5). In particular, factors associated with greater vulnerability to shocks (e.g., heightened occupational insecurity) should strengthen the translation of disruptive experiences into increased concern.

Box 1: Theoretical expectations and hypotheses

Based on our theoretical framework, we develop the following hypotheses:

- H1: Economic shocks lead to an increase in economic concerns.
- H2: Environmental shocks lead to an increase in environmental concerns.
- H3: Economic/environmental shocks reduce environmental/economic concerns.
- H4: Economic/environmental shocks increase environmental and economic concerns
- H5: The effects depend on contextual & individual factors shaping differential vulnerabilities

3. Methods and research design

3.1 Data

This analysis draws on a combination of survey, socioeconomic, and environmental data spanning the period 2003–2023. The primary dataset is the Standard Eurobarometer, a repeated cross-sectional series of public opinion surveys commissioned by the European Commission and carried out across European countries (including both EU member and non-member countries). Each wave employs a random, multistage sampling procedure and is designed to be nationally representative of the adult population. The surveys are typically fielded three times per year, which enables us to capture both long-term changes and short-term fluctuations in public opinion.

In total, we include data from 35 countries (Appendix Table A1) and harmonize information for 339 subnational regions (predominantly at the NUTS-2 level). Harmonization is necessary because the availability and classification of regional identifiers vary across waves. For surveys where the NUTS-2 code was not directly available, we reconstructed the regional identifier using region names and matched them to the 2016 NUTS-2 classification. To ensure robustness in matching across different languages and spellings, we employed fuzzy string-matching techniques. We additionally harmonized variables across survey waves to produce a consistent time series suitable for pooled cross-sectional analysis.

To contextualize survey responses with objective regional conditions, we integrate two complementary data sources. First, we use the Annual Regional Database of the European Commission (ARDECO), which provides annual information on population and socioeconomic indicators at the subnational level. From ARDECO, we construct measures of economic shocks. Second, we use climate reanalysis data from ERA5 (Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), 2023), which provides high-resolution (0.1°) hourly data on meteorological conditions. We aggregate temperature and precipitation data from ERA5 to the NUTS-2 level to capture local environmental shocks.

3.2 Measurement

Our main outcome variable captures respondents' concerns about different policy issues. In each Eurobarometer survey, respondents are asked what they consider to be the two most important issues facing their country at the moment. To ensure comparability over time, we harmonized the available answer categories across survey waves and grouped them into seven broader domains. These domains include concerns about the economy (such as inflation, prices, or unemployment); the environment, climate change, and energy related issues¹; immigration; security (crime, terrorism, or defence); education; health; and pensions. For each survey wave, we constructed binary indicators

¹ Until 2006, the Eurobarometer questionnaires included only one environment-related answer category, namely *“protecting the environment.”* In subsequent years, the list was expanded to add *“energy-related issues,”* and from 2011 onwards, both were merged into a single category, *“the environment, climate, and energy issues.”* To construct a harmonized time series of environmental concerns in Europe, we treated all responses referring to environmental issues as relevant, regardless of the specific formulation of answer categories across survey waves (see also Hoffmann et al., 2022). Since the occurrence of environmental and economic shocks is independent of the measurement approach, which was implemented simultaneously across all countries in the sample, we do not expect this variation in survey design to affect our main results.

measuring whether a respondent identified one of these domains among their two most important concerns.

Our key explanatory variables capture regional exposure to environmental and economic shocks. Environmental shocks are measured using temperature anomalies derived from ERA5 reanalysis data. Based on daily data, we calculate weekly anomalies and extreme temperature indices, given the calendar weekly distribution in the previous 30 years. These measures are temporally aggregated over the 52 weeks preceding start of interviews in each subnational region. Positive values reflect unusually warm conditions, while negative values indicate colder-than-average conditions relative to the long-term baseline.

We use temperature anomalies as our main indicator of environmental shocks, since extreme heat is closely linked to global warming and thus represents a highly salient environmental issue for survey respondents. Unlike other disruptive environmental events, such as floods or earthquakes, that tend to only have localized impacts, high temperatures generally exert more uniform effects on all respondents within a given subnational region. Economic shocks are measured by the regional unemployment rates at the time of the survey. As a robustness check, we additionally consider annual changes in GDP per capita at the subnational level to capture shifts in economic performance beyond employment trends. All results remain fully consistent to this variation.

In addition to these contextual measures, we include a set of individual-level controls available in the Eurobarometer to account for heterogeneity in concerns. Education is recoded into categories reflecting the age at which respondents completed formal education: less than 11 years, less than 15 years, less than 18 years, less than 25 years, less than 30 years, more than 30 years, and still studying. Occupation is grouped into broader employment categories, distinguishing higher professional and managerial positions, skilled and unskilled workers, agricultural workers (including farmers and fishermen), self-employed individuals such as shop owners, craftsmen, and small business proprietors, as well as service occupations. We also incorporate additional demographic characteristics, including age and sex, to control for systematic differences in individual perceptions of issues.

3.3 Estimation strategy

To assess the relationship between regional shocks and public concerns, we estimate linear fixed effects regression models that exploit the repeated cross-sectional structure of the Eurobarometer combined with regional time-series variation. The multilevel nature of the data allows us to incorporate both individual-level controls and regional fixed effects. Our main specification estimates the share of respondents in a region identifying a given issue as relevant conditional on the occurrence of regional economic and environmental shocks:

$$y_{rmy}^k = \beta T_{rmy} + \gamma U_{rmy} + \alpha_i + \theta_m + \delta_y + \varepsilon_{rmy}$$

where y_{rmy}^k refers to the average share of respondents in a subnational region r in a month m and year y who have concerns of the type k (environmental or economic) as the main outcome. T_{rmy} captures temperature anomalies that have taken place in the 52 weeks prior to the Eurobarometer data collection, and U_{rmy} the unemployment rate in the subnational region in the period of the Eurobarometer data collection. α_i are subnational region fixed effects (NUT2 level) that allow controlling for unobserved heterogeneity at the regional level, including relative stable differences in

economic development levels, degrees of urbanization, and cultural traits. In addition, we control for season θ_m and year δ_y fixed effects to account for temporal trends over time that might affect the results. All standard errors were clustered at the subnational regional level r .

In extended models, we perform interaction analyses to test for the interplay between the environmental and economic shock variables and different regional level contextual characteristics that may moderate the relationship. In addition, we replicate the above analysis at the individual level considering the effects of temperature anomalies and unemployment on the likelihood of a Eurobarometer respondent mentioning either environmental or economic issues as a main concern conditional on the occurrence of shocks. We further expand these micro-level models with subsample analyses considering the moderating influence of different occupations and education levels in explaining differences in response behaviours for men and women.

4. Results

4.1 Patterns of public concerns across Europe

Figure 2 illustrates patterns of public concerns about different policy issues over time (left panel) and across subnational regions in Europe (right panel). The regional distribution highlights the interplay between economic and environmental concerns by distinguishing regions with high levels of economic concerns, high levels of environmental concerns, or both. Here, different levels of concern are classified using a tertile split of the underlying distributions.

Across the full observation period, economic issues clearly dominate as the most important concern category. In most years, more than half of respondents identified economic problems among the two most important issues facing their country. The intensity of these concerns, however, has varied considerably over time. Following the European Financial Crisis, economic concerns peaked at around 80% of respondents identifying these as important, before stagnating and gradually declining after 2015. During this period, other issues, most notably immigration and security issues, gained prominence in public opinion.

Figure 2. Distribution of concerns for different policy issues across Europe. Panel A shows trends in public concerns between 2003 and 2023. Panel B presents a map of subnational regions, highlighting areas with heightened levels of economic concerns, environmental concerns, or both.

Environmental concerns followed a markedly different trajectory. In the early years of observation (2003–2005), fewer than 5% of respondents identified the environment as a top concern. After 2006, this share increased modestly to just above 10%, but it dropped sharply in the wake of the financial crisis, when economic concerns may have crowded out attention to other issues. Since 2015, however, environmental concerns have risen steadily, coinciding with the growing climate activism and policy debates across Europe. By the early 2020s, more than 20% of respondents on average across European regions considered environmental issues among the two most important ones facing their countries.

While in some periods, the trends in economic and environmental concerns are following opposite trajectories, most notably in the aftermath of the financial crisis, this pattern is not consistent across the full observation period. After 2017, for example, concerns about both the economy and the environment increased simultaneously. This suggests that the aggregate dynamics observed cannot be explained as a simple trade-off between the two policy issues (Drews et al., 2022; Ekinci & Van Lange, 2023; Evensen et al., 2021). Instead, other factors seem to be at play, determining whether trends in economic and environmental concerns are aligned over time or following opposite trajectories. These factors can include external shocks and disruptions, which determine whether an issue is considered relevant or not.

Considering the cross-sectional distribution of economic and environmental concerns across subnational regions in Europe, substantial heterogeneity is visible. Wealthier regions in Scandinavia and Western Europe tend to display heightened levels of environmental concern combined with

comparatively lower levels of economic concern, whereas less economically developed regions in Southern and Eastern Europe are on average more strongly characterized by economic concerns. At the same time, more mixed patterns are also visible. Several regions, most notably in Spain, parts of Italy, southern Norway, and Greece, exhibit simultaneously high levels of both economic and environmental concerns, underlining the diversity of regional concern profiles across Europe.

4.2 The effects of shocks on environmental and economic concerns

In the next step, we explicitly examine the drivers of economic and environmental concerns and assess whether trade-offs exist between these two types of issues. To do so, we consider contextual variation in local economic and environmental conditions, analysing how recent changes and external shocks shape political priorities and potentially divert attention from other issues, including concerns about the economy and the environment.

Table 1 presents the main findings from our baseline fixed-effects models at the subnational regional level. These aim to explain whether the share of respondents in a region expressing economic or environmental concerns is driven by the occurrence of economic and environmental shocks in the 52 weeks preceding each Eurobarometer survey. All variables are standardized, allowing for a direct comparison of effect sizes across different types of shocks. The models are estimated in a parsimonious way without additional control variables, accounting only for potential biases from unobserved regional heterogeneity, seasonality effects, and common time trends through the inclusion of region, season, and year fixed effects. Robustness checks, including alternative measures of economic shocks and the inclusion of individual-level controls, yield qualitatively similar results.

The findings indicate that both economic and environmental shocks and changes exert significant effects in the theoretically expected direction, supporting Hypotheses H1 and H2. Specifically, a one-standard-deviation increase in temperature anomalies in a region is associated with a 0.057 standard deviation increase (model 6) in the share of respondents reporting environmental concerns, while a one-standard-deviation increase in the unemployment rate corresponds to a 0.490 standard deviation increase (model 3) in the share of respondents reporting economic concerns.

Table 1. Results of fixed-effect models analysing the impacts of environmental and economic shocks on economic and environmental concern.

	Outcome variable:					
	Economic concerns			Environmental concerns		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Temperature anomaly	-0.040***		-0.048***	0.056***		0.057***
	(0.010)		(0.009)	(0.008)		(0.008)
Unemployment rate		0.488***	0.490***		-0.055***	-0.058***
		(0.014)	(0.014)		(0.013)	(0.013)
Observations	7,944	7,944	7,944	7,944	7,944	7,944
R2	0.313	0.404	0.407	0.476	0.474	0.478
Adjusted R2	0.285	0.379	0.382	0.454	0.452	0.456

Note: Coefficients from fixed effects models in cells with robust standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors were clustered at the NUTS-2 level. All models are estimated at the subnational regional level. The outcome variables capture the share of respondents who considered either economic issues or environmental issues as the two most important issues facing their country at the moment. The explanatory variables capture the average temperature anomaly and unemployment rate in the 52 weeks prior to the Eurobarometer interview date. Both the outcome and explanatory variables were standardized to allow for comparisons across the models. All models control for season, year, and NUT2 fixed effects. P-Values: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

At the same time, the models reveal evidence of trade-offs between concern types, consistent with Hypothesis H3. An environmental shock of one standard deviation is associated with a 0.48 percentage point reduction in the share of respondents expressing economic concerns (Model 3), while an unemployment shock of one standard deviation reduces the share of respondents expressing environmental concerns by 0.058 standard deviations. These patterns suggest that, under conditions of stress, public attention is partially reallocated: increases in concern about one issue can reduce attention to other relevant topics.

While a general pattern of trade-offs emerges, their magnitude differs across policy domains. Increases in environmental concerns following temperature anomalies are accompanied by reductions in economic concerns of a comparable size. By contrast, the rise in economic concerns in response to unemployment shocks is much larger than the corresponding decline in environmental concerns ($0.490 > 0.058$). This asymmetry suggests that during periods of environmental stress, individuals tend to shift attention from economic to environmental issues, whereas in times of economic stress, environmental concerns remain more stable.

4.3 Interactions between different types of shocks

To further investigate the trade-offs between economic and environmental concerns, we examine how these concerns respond to the joint occurrence of economic and environmental shocks. If the formation of concerns operated independently across domains, the simultaneous experience of different types of disruptions would not be expected to have additional effects. Table 2 presents the results of fixed-effects models at the subnational regional level, which analyze how interactions between shocks shape changes in concerns across Europe.

Table 2. Results of fixed-effect models analysing the joint impacts and interactions of environmental and economic shocks on economic and environmental concern.

	Outcome variable:	
	Economic concerns (1)	Environmental concerns (2)
Temperature anomaly	-0.0485*** (0.0108)	0.0582*** (0.0086)
Unemployment rate	0.5123*** (0.0422)	-0.0579** (0.0214)
Temperature anomaly × Unemployment rate	0.0450*** (0.0096)	-0.0407*** (0.0068)
Observations	7,944	7,944
R2	0.596	0.667
Adjusted R2	0.578	0.652

Note: Coefficients from fixed effects models in cells with robust standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors were clustered at the NUTS-2 level. All models are estimated at the subnational regional level. The outcome variables capture the share of respondents who considered either economic issues or environmental issues as the two most important issues facing their country at the moment. The explanatory variables capture the average temperature anomaly and unemployment rate in the 52 weeks prior to the Eurobarometer interview date. Both the outcome and explanatory variables were standardized to allow for comparisons across the models. All models control for season, year, and NUT2 fixed effects. P-Values: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

The findings indicate that interactions between shocks play an important role in explaining changes in concerns over time. When environmental and economic shocks occur in isolation, their effects remain largely consistent with the baseline models presented in Table 1. However, when shocks co-occur, respondents appear to prioritize economic over environmental issues. Specifically, while temperature anomalies reduce economic concerns under favourable economic conditions, this dampening effect is substantially weaker (0.0450) during periods of increasing unemployment. Likewise, the positive effect of environmental shocks on environmental concerns is markedly smaller (-0.0407) during such periods of economic hardship.

This suggests that economic issues can crowd out environmental concerns, whereas favourable economic conditions create more space for environmental issues to be recognized as important. When environmental stress occurs in isolation, it can be a dominant driver of shifts in both environmental and economic concerns. Yet when people face simultaneous pressures, the urgency of economic security tends to overshadow worries about environmental change. These dynamics highlight the importance of contextual conditions in shaping public concern: environmental issues are not fixed priorities but are contingent on the broader social and economic environment.

4.4 Contextual factors moderate the effects of shocks on concerns

We expect the influence of environmental and economic shocks to depend on contextual factors that shape how strongly Eurobarometer respondents are affected by external disruptions. To explore these moderating effects, we estimate a series of interaction models, interacting the shock variables with regional characteristics that capture long-term socioeconomic conditions at the NUTS-2 level. Specifically, we interact the shocks with average education levels, unemployment rates, and GDP per capita at the regional level. All interaction variables are standardized to facilitate direct comparison of effects.

Figure 3 illustrates how the marginal effects of environmental and economic shocks on both economic concerns (red line) and environmental concerns (blue line) vary with the average level of education (age of completed education), unemployment share, and GDP per capita in the subnational regions. The averages of these interaction variables are calculated from the observations over the entire sampling period to capture long-term socioeconomic differences between the subnational regions.

The results show that all three socioeconomic characteristics systematically shape how shocks translate into public concern. In particular, the effect of environmental shocks on environmental concerns becomes considerably stronger in regions with higher levels of education, lower unemployment, and greater wealth. At the same time, shifts in economic concerns, both upward and downward, are also more pronounced in these more advantaged regions in response to both environmental and economic shocks. This suggests that populations in regions with higher socioeconomic status generally exhibit stronger reactions to external disruptions and short-term changes in environmental and economic conditions.

Figure 3. The moderating influence of socioeconomic contexts in shaping environmental and economic concerns. The *x*-axis shows the long-term level of education, unemployment, and GDP per capita in the NUTS-2 regions of the Eurobarometer respondents. The *y*-axis shows the marginal effects of the environmental (top panels) and economic (bottom panels) shocks on both economic (red lines) and environmental (blue lines) concerns, respectively (see Appendix Table A2-A4 for full models).

One possible explanation is that better-educated and wealthier (often more urban) populations are more responsive to evolving issues because they have greater access to information and are thus more attuned to such concerns. By contrast, populations in regions with lower socio-economic status may exhibit more stable concern patterns, focused primarily on a limited set of pressing challenges most relevant to their immediate context. Consistent with earlier results, we find that economic concerns are more volatile, responding to both environmental and economic shocks, while environmental concerns are particularly sensitive to environmental shocks and only weakly negatively affected by economic shocks.

4.5 Robustness check: Effects of shocks at the individual level

To further explore the relationship between environmental and economic concerns and external shocks, we replicate our main regional-level analysis at the individual level. Considering changes in concerns among Eurobarometer respondents over time not only allows us to test the robustness of our earlier findings, but also to examine who at the individual level is most strongly affected by shocks and why.

Table 3 reports the results of fixed-effects models that analyse differences in each respondent's economic and environmental concerns. In particular, we are interested whether the exposure to temperature anomalies and changes in unemployment in the subnational regions over time had an effect on the individual concern levels. As in the regional-level models, we control for subnational region, season, and year fixed effects to account for unobserved heterogeneity. In addition, we account for respondents' education level (age of completed education), age, sex, and occupation status as relevant control variables.

The results are largely consistent with our main findings in Table 1. Environmental shocks increase environmental concerns while reducing economic concerns, whereas economic shocks increase economic concerns and, to a lesser degree, reduce environmental concerns. Education, age, sex, and occupation exert significant effects on the levels of concern: Those with higher education have lower economic and higher environmental concerns; both types of concern are higher among younger age groups; and women have on average lower levels of economic and higher levels of environmental concerns. Among the different occupational groups, highest levels of economic concerns are recorded among the unemployed and self-employed who serve as a reference group in the models. For environmental concerns, we observe the highest levels among the self-employed and employed occupational categories.

Table 3. Results of fixed-effect models analysing the effect of environmental and economic shocks on environmental and economic concern at the individual level.

	Outcome variable (binary)					
	Economic concerns			Environmental concerns		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Temperature anomaly	-0.032*** (0.004)		-0.032*** (0.004)		0.067*** (0.003)	0.067*** (0.003)
Unemployment rate		0.021*** (0.0002)	0.021*** (0.0002)	0.0003** (0.0001)		0.0003** (0.0001)
Education	-0.0004*** (0.00004)	-0.001*** (0.00004)	-0.0005*** (0.00004)	0.001*** (0.00003)	0.001*** (0.00003)	0.001*** (0.00003)
Age	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.0001***	-0.0001***	-0.0001***

	(0.00003)	(0.00003)	(0.00003)	(0.00002)	(0.00002)	(0.00002)
Sex (ref: Male)	-0.001	-0.002**	-0.002**	0.006***	0.006***	0.006***
	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)
Occupation reference: Self-employed						
Occupation: employed	-0.016***	-0.015***	-0.015***	-0.002	-0.002	-0.002
	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.003)	(0.003)	(0.003)
Occupation: retired	-0.036***	-0.036***	-0.037***	-0.010***	-0.010***	-0.010***
	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.003)	(0.003)	(0.003)
Occupation: student	-0.032***	-0.027***	-0.027***	-0.017***	-0.016***	-0.016***
	(0.005)	(0.005)	(0.005)	(0.003)	(0.003)	(0.003)
Occupation: unemployed	0.052***	0.043***	0.043***	-0.019***	-0.019***	-0.019***
	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.003)	(0.003)	(0.003)
Observations	948,948	828,591	827,256	828,591	948,948	827,256
R2	0.049	0.063	0.063	0.053	0.053	0.054
Adjusted R2	0.049	0.063	0.063	0.053	0.053	0.054

Note: Coefficients from fixed effects models in cells with robust standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors were clustered at the NUTS-2 level. All models are estimated at the individual level of the Eurobarometer respondents. The binary outcome variables capture whether respondents considered either economic issues or environmental issues as the two most important issues facing their country at the moment. The explanatory variables capture the average temperature anomaly and unemployment rate in the 52 weeks prior to the Eurobarometer interview date. Both the outcome and shock variables were standardized to allow for comparisons across the models. All models control for season, year, and NUT2 fixed effects. P-Values: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

The age patterns can be explained in several ways. Economic concerns tend to be less salient for older respondents, many of whom may already be retired or otherwise less directly exposed to fluctuations in employment and income. Younger respondents, by contrast, are more likely to be active in the labour market, facing greater uncertainty in employment prospects and income stability, which can heighten their sensitivity to economic shocks. At the same time, younger generations have generally grown up in a context where climate change is a prominent political and social issue (Thiery et al., 2021). They will be the ones worst affected by the climate crisis and may therefore feel the urgency of the issue more compared to older respondents. This may translate into stronger environmental awareness and greater responsiveness to environmental shocks, even when faced with competing economic pressures.

The effects by education and occupation likely reflect differences in socioeconomic status and related forms of cultural and economic capital. Respondents with higher education tend to report lower levels of economic concern, possibly because higher socioeconomic status provides greater financial security and buffers against economic shocks. At the same time, education is strongly associated with greater access to information, higher political engagement, and stronger pro-

environmental values. These mechanisms can help explain why environmental concerns are consistently higher among more educated respondents as well as those in employment. People with a higher socioeconomic status may also have sufficient means to care more about the environment being economically more protected, while this may not be the case for more disadvantaged groups.

4.6 Individual-level heterogeneity

To further consider how the effects of external environmental and economic shocks vary by individual characteristics of the respondents, we run a series of sub-sample models. These models break down the large Eurobarometer sample into smaller sub-groups to explore how the regional occurrence of temperature anomalies and unemployment prior to the survey date had differential effects (y-axis) on different groups distinguishing respondents by their level of education (x-axis), occupation (different column panels), and sex (different colours).

Across all categories, except for the small occupational category of agriculture, people are more concerned about the economy after economic shocks and about the environment after environmental shocks. Better educated respondents (who finished their education after the age of 18) respond more strongly to environmental shocks by increasing their environmental concerns and reducing their economic concerns. Lower educated respondents (who finished their education before the age of 18), on the other hand, were found to respond more strongly to economic shocks, suggesting greater vulnerability to these types of shocks in line with hypothesis H5. We only find minor differences by the sex of the respondents.

Figure 4. Differences in the effects of economic and environmental shocks by respondents' characteristics. *The figures show differences in the marginal effects (y-axis) of both shock types (column panels) on the two concern categories (row panels) for different education groups (x-axis) and sexes (colours). We distinguish between respondents with high (age of completed education > 18 years) and low to moderate levels (age of completed education < 18 years) of formal education. The figure shows the coefficient estimates and 95% CI (bars) of the marginal effects of the shocks on the concern outcomes. The effects were estimated in 16 models based on sub-samples of the total Eurobarometer respondents distinguishing 2 education groups, 4 occupational categories, and 2 sexes (See Appendix Table A5 for sample description).*

5. Discussion

Based on harmonized Eurobarometer surveys, we show that there are pronounced differences in levels of environmental and economic concerns between European subnational regions. These average differences are related to persistent institutional, political, and cultural characteristics. High levels of environmental concerns are found in Northern and Western European countries with high income levels, developed social security systems, and established green parties which provide platforms to systematically politicize environmental issues. At the same time, material economic concerns in this context are, on average, relatively low compared to other European regions.

In contrast, environmental concerns remain comparatively uncommon in Southern and Eastern European countries while economic issues are prioritized more frequently. In particular, post-socialist countries exhibit unique characteristics. Their contexts of relative economic insecurity and recent history of authoritarian regimes may likely not be as favourable for bottom-up support of green agendas and individual willingness to sacrifice for the environment despite awareness of environmental issues (Marquart-Pyatt, 2012). However, there are also some areas in these regions in which respondents jointly indicate environmental and economic concern as important, highlighting idiosyncrasies on subnational level.

Both environmental and economic concerns vary substantially over time. Our regression models indicate that disruptive changes in economic and environmental conditions shape concern levels. Worsening economic conditions, as measured by regional unemployment rates, increase economic concern while slightly decreasing environmental concern. The relatively modest size of this latter effect suggests that the trade-off between environmental and economic priorities may not be as strong as sometimes assumed, calling into question the notion that environmental concerns are consistently crowded out during economic disruptions.

At the same time, we find that the co-occurrence of different types of shocks clearly favors economic over environmental concerns. While environmental shocks in isolation can significantly influence both environmental and economic concerns, their impact is substantially diminished during periods of economic hardship and rising unemployment. Overall, economic concerns are more volatile and reactive to both types of shocks, whereas environmental concerns tend to be more stable. This stability, however, is conditional: environmental priorities are resilient in periods of relative economic security but are more sensitive when simultaneous economic pressures demand attention, highlighting the context-dependent and dynamic nature of public concerns.

The relationships between both environmental and economic shocks and concerns are more pronounced in regions with relatively high level of education, low unemployment, and high income, suggesting that favourable economic conditions could be related to changes in concerns. We find similar patterns on the individual level. For instance, the environmental and economic concerns of employees with lower education are more strongly affected by changes in unemployment than of those with higher education, possibly because their occupations tend to be more susceptible to economic disruptions. Overall, the evidence suggests that changes in environmental and economic conditions, regional characteristics, and individuals' economic situation interact to produce the concern patterns observed in our data (Marquart-Pyatt, 2012; Mayer & Smith, 2017).

Our results come with limitations that are important to consider when interpreting the findings. First, the design of the Eurobarometer trend questions, that our measures of concern for different topics are based on, may affect the observed levels and changes of concern (Höpner & Urczyk, 2012). For example, there are more answer items related to economic issues than for other domains, which may make respondents more inclined to express economic concerns. In addition, answer items for

the environmental concern variable have changed over time. Since these changes have been simultaneously introduced in all countries in the dataset and are likely uncorrelated with the shock variables considered in our models, we do not expect them to affect our main results. However, they can be relevant for the interpretation of the general trends observed in the data.

Second, while the Eurobarometer concern measures capture respondents' stated concerns about the economy and the environment, they do not reflect their willingness to take action (Hoffmann et al., 2024). Prioritizing an issue does not necessarily translate into behavioural change, and concerns about the environment or the economy may be both high as long as individuals are not required to make costly or personally disadvantageous adjustments (Diekmann & Preisendörfer, 2003).

Third, the assessment of concerns is based on respondents' perception of the two most relevant concerns facing their country at the moment. The restriction to only two concerns by measurement design introduces a trade-off in the selection process, i.e. choosing one topic implies foregoing another one. The opposite signs of the effects on environmental and economic concerns could be related to this mechanism to some extent. Finally, the moderators in Figures 3 and 4 are correlated with unobserved regional characteristics, including those discussed above, implying that the analysis of possible mechanisms should be interpreted as exploratory.

The findings point towards several avenues of future research. First, our study could be extended to psychological antecedents such as issue attention and values, as well as outcomes such as policy support and voting behaviour. This could provide more nuanced insights into emotional and cognitive processes at the individual level. Second, we identified some regions in which economic and environmental concerns coexist. These regions could serve as case studies to better understand how environmental concerns can be sustained in times of economic crises. Third, each recession has unique features and may differ in its effects on popular concern, which offers room for further exploration. In the COVID-19 recession, for example, environmental concern remained relatively stable compared to the 2008 economic recession, possibly due to similarities of pandemic and climate change policy issues (Drews et al., 2022; Evensen et al., 2021; Gregersen et al., 2022; Shao, 2025; Stefkovics et al., 2024).

Our findings also provide useful insights into how to communicate about environmental issues in periods of economic challenges and other crises (Botzen et al., 2021). Communication strategies should recognize that environmental concerns are more likely to be crowded out when economic pressures are high, and framing policies in ways that minimize perceived economic costs may help maintain public support. Targeted messaging toward groups with higher vulnerability to economic shocks, including those with lower socioeconomic status, could prevent disengagement and ensure broader resonance. Additionally, emphasizing co-benefits of environmental action, such as job creation or energy savings, may help align environmental priorities with economic concerns during times of crisis. In this regard, policies that help buffer the impacts of economic shocks, such as unemployment support, social safety nets, or income stabilization measures, can generate important co-benefits by sustaining public engagement with environmental protection efforts.

6. Conclusions

In this study, we combine harmonized Eurobarometer survey data with socioeconomic and environmental data for 339 subnational regions across 35 European countries between 2003 and 2023. To capture economic and environmental shocks and disruptions, we linked the survey data to regional unemployment statistics from ARDECO and high-resolution climate reanalysis data from ERA5. Temperature anomalies serve as our primary indicator of environmental shocks, while annual changes in unemployment rates capture economic shocks. This design enables us to analyse how changes in economic and environmental conditions have jointly shaped patterns of concern across European countries.

Our study demonstrates that environmental and economic concerns across European regions are shaped by both persistent structural characteristics and short-term shocks. Trade-offs between the different types of concerns are visible: Economic disruptions increase economic concerns and lead to a reduction in environmental concerns, although to a lesser extent. At the same time, environmental shocks not only raise environmental concern but also coincide with a reduction in economic concern. If both types of shocks co-occur, respondents typically prioritize economic over environmental issues. These dynamics unfold against a backdrop of strong cross-regional variation, with Northern and Western Europe displaying higher levels of environmental concern and Southern and Eastern Europe prioritizing economic issues more strongly, reflecting institutional, political, and cultural legacies.

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Appendix

Table A1: Summary statistics for countries included in the dataset (averages over all survey waves)

Country	Region	Average pos. temp. anomaly	Average unemployment rate	Average economic concern	Average environmental concern
Albania	12	0.223	15.1	78.4	5.78
Austria	9	0.218	4.6	71.4	12.51
Belgium	11	0.207	7.3	71.5	14.30
Bulgaria	6	0.217	7.5	80.2	5.76
Croatia	1	0.230	11.2	85.5	3.38
Cyprus	1	0.235	8.1	80.5	4.11
Czechia	8	0.196	4.9	68.3	9.28
Denmark	6	0.245	5.4	48.6	28.25
Estonia	1	0.198	7.2	76.2	11.21
Finland	4	0.212	8.1	69.0	17.33
France	21	0.229	8.1	76.8	10.79
Germany	21	0.227	7.0	59.7	15.86
Greece	10	0.227	17.2	88.7	3.34
Hungary	8	0.222	5.8	69.6	7.28
Iceland	1	0.143	5.7	66.3	19.35
Ireland	1	0.146	7.4	61.3	7.54
Italy	5	0.283	9.7	81.9	6.35
Latvia	6	0.195	9.4	82.8	3.85
Lithuania	10	0.196	8.9	84.9	4.98
Luxembourg	1	0.227	5.3	64.9	10.93
Malta	1	0.305	4.6	46.3	22.88
Montenegro	1	0.263	17.3	77.2	5.36
Netherlands	12	0.212	4.7	53.8	20.29
Norway	6	0.193	3.2	72.7	38.76
Poland	17	0.196	8.5	74.4	6.98

Country	Region	Average pos. temp. anomaly	Average unemployment rate	Average economic concern	Average environmental concern
Portugal	7	0.214	9.0	85.4	2.40
Romania	8	0.225	5.7	72.3	7.19
Serbia	5	0.219	14.1	76.3	6.76
Slovakia	4	0.211	10.2	77.5	8.25
Slovenia	12	0.228	6.4	76.0	6.77
Spain	16	0.229	13.7	73.8	4.55
Sweden	11	0.219	7.2	54.8	24.61
Switzerland	7	0.245	4.7	43.9	53.10
Turkey	35	0.251	9.4	75.1	2.74
United Kingdom	13	0.173	5.6	50.9	6.88

Table A2: Results of a fixed effect model to analyse the effect of environmental shocks on economic concerns along contextual variables

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Temperature anomaly	-0.0376** (0.0126)	-0.0433*** (0.0120)	-0.0398** (0.0127)
seasonspring	-0.0075 (0.0132)	-0.0085 (0.0132)	-0.0072 (0.0132)
seasonsummer	0.1198** (0.0401)	0.1262** (0.0401)	0.1236** (0.0403)
seasonwinter	0.1663*** (0.0447)	0.1717*** (0.0448)	0.1682*** (0.0449)
tmean_ano_pos_52w_scale × mean_educ_scale	-0.0337*** (0.0079)		
tmean_ano_pos_52w_scale × mean_unemploy_scale		0.0372*** (0.0104)	
tmean_ano_pos_52w_scale × mean_gdp_scale			-0.0243** (0.0093)

Num.Obs.	7934	7934	7934
R2	0.533	0.533	0.533
R2 Adj.	0.514	0.514	0.513
R2 Within	0.315	0.315	0.314
R2 Within Adj.	0.313	0.313	0.312
AIC	17232.4	17233.5	17244.7
BIC	19444.7	19445.9	19457.0
RMSE	0.69	0.69	0.69
Std.Errors	by: NUTS_ID	by: NUTS_ID	by: NUTS_ID
FE: NUTS_ID	X	X	X

Note: + $p < 0.1$; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Table A3: Results of a fixed effect model to analyse the effect of economic shocks on environmental concerns along contextual variables

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Unemployment rate	-0.1112*** (0.0293)	-0.1094*** (0.0264)	-0.1240*** (0.0268)
seasonspring	-0.0812*** (0.0098)	-0.0809*** (0.0099)	-0.0814*** (0.0097)
seasonsummer	0.0037 (0.0243)	0.0040 (0.0242)	0.0044 (0.0240)
seasonwinter	-0.1299*** (0.0337)	-0.1326*** (0.0342)	-0.1316*** (0.0335)
unempl_rate_52w_scale × mean_educ_scale	-0.2156*** (0.0533)		
unempl_rate_52w_scale × mean_unemploy_scale		0.0667*** (0.0163)	
unempl_rate_52w_scale × mean_gdp_scale			-0.1731*** (0.0361)
Num.Obs.	7934	7934	7934
R2	0.668	0.665	0.669

R2 Adj.	0.654	0.651	0.655
R2 Within	0.481	0.477	0.483
R2 Within Adj.	0.480	0.476	0.481
AIC	14347.3	14407.8	14327.8
BIC	16559.6	16620.1	16540.1
RMSE	0.57	0.58	0.57
Std.Errors	by: NUTS_ID	by: NUTS_ID	by: NUTS_ID
FE: NUTS_ID	X	X	X

Note: + $p < 0.1$; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Table A4: Results of a fixed effect model to analyse the effect of environmental shocks on economic concerns along contextual variables

	Dependent variable:	
	p_economy_m2	p_env_m2
	(1)	(2)
Temperature anomaly	-0.037*** (0.010)	
Unemployment rate		-0.016* (0.009)
gdp_pc	-0.774*** (0.072)	0.323*** (0.064)
p_educ_mt25	-0.105*** (0.017)	0.157*** (0.015)
average_age	-0.011 (0.013)	-0.041*** (0.012)
seasonspring	0.025 (0.021)	-0.100*** (0.019)
seasonsummer	0.120** (0.052)	0.010 (0.046)
seasonwinter	0.155*** (0.059)	-0.128** (0.052)
Observations	6,658	6,658
R2	0.383	0.526

Adjusted R2

0.352

0.503

Note: $p < 0.1$; $p < 0.05$; $p < 0.01$

Table A5: Sample size for individual-level regressions displayed in Figure 4.

Age upon leaving education	Sex	Occupation	Sample size
18+	female	agriculture	1270
18+	male	agriculture	2817
18+	female	employed	208380
18+	male	employed	179829
18+	female	retired	68307
18+	male	retired	67392
18+	female	unemploy	21015
18+	male	unemploy	15301
18-	female	agriculture	2909
18-	male	agriculture	7429
18-	female	employed	189148
18-	male	employed	151557
18-	female	retired	134550
18-	male	retired	114553
18-	female	unemploy	32441
18-	male	unemploy	28085

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